

Studies in Electrokinetic Properties of Charcoal Dispersions. Part I. Electrophoretic Measurements in Relation to Chemisorbed Oxygen

Balwant Rai Puri, Kuljit Singh, and N. K. Sandle

Charcoal particles in aqueous suspension carry negative charge. The electrophoretic mobility decreases with increase in the amount of that part of the chemisorbed oxygen which comes off as CO_2 on high-temperature evacuation. The rest of the chemisorbed oxygen does not influence this property. On the addition of small concentrations of electrolytes, preferential adsorption of anions occurs, resulting in an increase of zeta-potential. The relative increase is less in the case of electrolytes with polyvalent cations.

Although a considerable amount of work has been reported on the effect of chemisorbed oxygen or prior heat treatment in altering adsorption characteristics and surface acidity of charcoal¹⁻⁶, the effect of the same on electrokinetic properties has not received sufficient attention. Kruyt and de Kadt⁷ through electrophoretic measurements on charcoal systems showed that the particles in aqueous suspension carried negative charge, which diminished on heating at increasing temperatures in carbon dioxide and was reversed on heating at 950°. Although Bakh⁸ confirmed these observations, Olin⁹ and Bennister and King¹⁰, on the contrary, reported that electrophoretic mobility of charcoal particles increased with increase in the temperature of activation in moist oxygen from 380° to 850° and decreased markedly thereafter; but there was no reversal of charge at 950° or 1000°. Although it is well known that the amount and nature of the combined oxygen vary considerably with variation in the temperature of activation or prior heat treatment, these workers, reporting conflicting observations, did not adduce any evidence for the influence of the surface-oxygen complexes on electrophoretic mobility or the ζ -potential of the charcoal particles in aqueous suspension. The present investigation was therefore undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar charcoal, prepared in the same manner as described earlier¹¹, was used as such (when it is referred to as 'original' charcoal in the text) as well as after outgassing at 400°,

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2. Puri *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1958, **62**, 756.
3. Garten and Weiss, *Rev. Pure & Appl. Chem.*, 1957, **7**, 69.
4. Weller and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 4155.
5. Wilson and Bolam, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1950, **5**, 550.
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7. *Kolloid Z.*, 1929, **47**, 44.
8. *Acta Physicochim.*, *USSR.*, 1941, **16**, 463.
9. Olin *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1935, **27**, 690.
10. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 991.
11. Puri *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1963, 4980.

600°, 750°, 1000°, and 1200°. The heated samples were allowed to cool in nitrogen atmosphere and then stored in tightly corked bottles, flushed with nitrogen, till required for further use. The amount of oxygen retained and the form in which it was disposed of (as CO₂, CO, and H₂O) were determined in the manner described earlier^{9,11}. The results are recorded in Table I. The outgassed materials were also treated with HNO₃ (conc.) to bring about surface oxidation. For this purpose, charcoal (10 g.) was heated with pure nitric acid (300 ml) in a pyrex beaker over a low flame till the volume was reduced to about 20 ml. It was made to 300 ml with distilled water and again heated gently to dryness. The residue was heated to 120° in an air-oven for about 5 hr. and then outgassed at 150°. It was stored in the atmosphere of nitrogen till required. This treatment resulted in the loss of some carbon and the addition of an appreciable amount of oxygen, most of which was found to come off as carbon dioxide on high-temperature evacuation, as shown in Table I. The amount of nitrogen fixed, as determined by micro-analysis technique, was found to be less than 0.2%.

TABLE I

Amounts of gases evolved on evacuating diff. samples of sugar charcoal at 1200°.

Samples.	Oxygen evolved on evacuation as:			Free hydrogen evolved.	Total oxygen evolved as CO ₂ etc.	
	CO ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ O.			
Original	109.9	73.9	71.6	15.2	255.4	
Evacuated at 400°	42.4	68.2	51.1	15.1	161.7	
600°	7.6	56.7	39.1	15.1	103.4	
750°	Nil	55.4	13.4	12.0	68.8	
1000°	..	5.7	Nil	1.1	5.7	
1200°	..	Nil	..	Nil	Nil	
Degassed	400° & HNO ₃ -treated	244.5	78.1	46.2	8.1	368.8
600°	..	201.2	75.0	30.1	6.1	306.3
750°	..	184.3	64.2	32.4	5.9	280.9
1000°	..	164.1	37.3	29.5	2.7	230.9
1200°	..	167.2	85.1	34.3	5.0	286.6

N. B. Figures expressed in mg./g.

The strength of the charcoal dispersions, used in electrophoretic experiments, was about 0.5%. The nitric acid-treated charcoals provided fine dispersions when added to water and shaken for a few minutes. The rest of the samples were ground to a thick paste in a pestle and mortar for about 2 hours. Electrophoretic mobility was determined by the moving boundary method^{12,13}. The reproducibility was checked in a number of cases by varying the time as well as the potential gradient (between 4 to 6 volts/cm) and the values were in agreement within 3% of one another.

12. Freundlich and Zeh, *Z physikal Chem.*, 1925, 114, 65.

13. Kruyt and Willigen, *Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 44, 22.

TABLE II

Sample.	Electrophoretic mobility (cm. $\times 10^{-6}$).	$-\zeta$ potential.
Original	-138	21.88 mv
Evacuated at		
400°	-196	31.58
600°	-228	36.75
750°	-240	38.68
1000°	-244	39.32
1200°	-242	38.99
400° & HNO ₃ -treated	- 29	4.87
000° "	- 44	7.09
750° "	- 69	11.12
1000° "	- 76	12.24
1200° "	-114	18.37

DISCUSSION

The electrophoretic mobility of charcoal particles has been found to increase appreciably on outgassing at increasing temperatures to 750° and then tend to acquire, more or less, a constant value. The zeta-potential (ζ), as calculated by the equation:

$$\zeta = \frac{4 \pi \eta \mu}{D}$$

(where μ is electrophoretic mobility and D and η are dielectric constant and viscosity of the medium respectively) was found to be 21.88 mv in the case of the original charcoal and to increase up to 38.68 mv on outgassing at 750°.

The electrophoretic mobility (and so the ζ -potential) of the outgassed charcoals after treatment with HNO₃(conc.) decreases considerably without showing any reversal of the charge in any case.

Fig. 1 shows that electrophoretic mobility is fairly closely connected with the amount of oxygen that comes off as carbon dioxide, and not at all with the total combined oxygen.

It has already been shown^{1,2,14} that it is the CO₂-complex, which determines acid behaviour, polar nature, and lyophilic character of charcoal and that the rest of the oxygen is not involved at all in influencing these properties. The results presented here show that it is this complex, which alone influences electrophoretic mobility of charcoal particles, the rest of the combined oxygen having no significance in this respect. Incidentally, the charcoal, outgassed at 750°, retains about 5.5% of oxygen, disposed of as CO (Table I), but little or no change in ζ -potential (Table II) is observed when this oxygen is progressively eliminated on outgassing at 1000° and 1200°.

The relationship, plotted in Fig. 1, shows that the ζ -potential varies inversely as the CO₂-complex, irrespective of the fact whether the change in the amount of the CO₂-complex has been brought about by outgassing or by subsequent treatment with HNO₃. Thus it is

14. Puri *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1958, 50, 1071.

not the treatment but the amount of the CO_2 -complex which, in the case of a given charcoal, has a marked effect on electrophoretic mobility. The inverse relationship between the amount of CO_2 -complex and the magnitude of negative ζ -potential may be explained as follows.

FIG. 1. Effect of chemisorbed oxygen on electrophoretic mobility of charcoal dispersions in water.

Carbon has the characteristic property, like carborundum, glass, etc., to preferentially adsorb hydroxyl ions from water and possibly also anions from an electrolyte, if present. A corresponding number of positive ions, some held in the fixed part and the rest in the diffused part of the double layer, will remain in the liquid. Now if CO_2 -complex is also present, charcoal will undergo surface ionisation, as has been shown previously¹⁵, when suspended in water, as

The hydrogen ions in this case, though directed towards the liquid phase, do not part company from the surface and the effect is similar to that caused by the concentration of the oppositely charged ions on the surface. As is well known, this leads to decrease in the charge density and thickness of the double layer and consequent decrease in the ζ -potential. As the CO_2 -complex is gradually eliminated on outgassing at increasing temperatures, the extent of surface ionisation, as represented above, decreases and therefore ζ increases correspondingly. Since the rest of the combined oxygen, disposed of as CO or H_2O , does not lead to surface ionisation, its presence does not materially alter the magnitude of the electrophoretic mobility or ζ .

TABLE III

Electrolyte conc.	Mobility on the addition of electrolytes.					
	Original charcoal.			Evacuated at 400°		
	KCl.	BaCl ₂ .	AlCl ₃ .	KCl.	BaCl ₂ .	AlCl ₃ .
Nil	136	136	136	196	196	196
0.000001N	137	137	136	201	198	197
0.0001	153	139	137	221	217	204
0.001	291	239	182	301	259	220
	Evacuated at 750°			Evacuated at 1200°.		
Nil	240	240	240	242	242	242
0.000001N	269	248	243	244	243	244
0.0001	346	298	251	320	317	259
0.001	415	..	337	307	331	302

The effect of adding increasing concentrations of potassium chloride, barium chloride, and aluminium chloride on electrophoretic mobility of the original and some of the out-gassed charcoals is shown in Table III. The addition of an electrolyte, even like AlCl₃, far from lowering the negative ζ -potential, actually raises it. This can only be attributed to preferential adsorption of the anions (Cl⁻ ions) at the charcoal surface. This increases the $-\zeta$ and confers additional stability on the system. The counter ions, *i.e.*, the metallic cations, unlike the hydrogen ions (furnished by the surface ionisation of charcoal when CO₂-complex is present), which remain exclusively on the surface, are present only partly in the fixed part and the rest are in the diffused portion of the double layer and therefore at lower electrolyte concentrations do not counteract the charge density or ζ of the system. But the antagonistic action of the cations is evident even at these low concentrations since the relative increase in electrophoretic mobility for the same concentrations of different electrolytes decreases with increase in the valency of the cation.